

Assessment of the Physical and Chemical Potability of Groundwater in Senegal

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Abstract:- Most of the groundwater in Senegal is not recommended directly for consumption. The diagnosis of groundwater shows that more than 80% of the water withdrawn from different areas of Senegal does not respect the WHO recommendation values. Parameters in excess pose serious health risks, their presence may indicate that the groundwater is poor quality and may be indicative of the existence of other problems that may have harmful effects on health. The main objective of this study is therefore to correlate the physical and chemical parameters of groundwater samples with respect to the different sampling areas and to assess their representativeness. To achieve this objective, we used the method of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and the Hierarchical Ascending Classification (HAC) of the statistical analysis tool (STATISTICA Application) on the results of physical and chemical analyzes in order to better interpret the different parameters.

Keywords:- Physical and Chemical Parameters, Groundwater, Chemometrics, Regions, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Hierarchical Ascending Classification (HAC).

I. INTRODUCTION

The available natural water reserves are made up of groundwater, stagnant or flowing surface water and seawater [1]. Groundwater is all water below the ground surface, in the saturation zone and in direct contact with the ground or subsoil. Underground aquifers mainly contain the freshwater reserve (96%) that can be exploited on land [2, 3]. Their pumping is divided into the following uses: 65% for irrigation, 25% for drinking water and 10% for industry.

The geological nature of the terrain has a major influence on the chemical composition of groundwater. At all times, the water is in contact with the ground in which it stagnates or circulates: a balance is established between the composition of the ground and that of the water. The waters circulating in a sandy or granitic subsoil are acidic and have little mineral content. The waters circulating in calcareous soils are calcium bicarbonate and often have a high hardness [4, 5]. In the case of karstic waters, however, we can note sudden variations in quality, with the appearance of turbidity and various types of pollution [6-8]. These variations are linked to the rainfall and to the runoff entrained without any real filtration in the underground network. Of particular note is good

bacteriological purity, low turbidity, constant temperature, chemical composition and the almost general absence of oxygen causing the presence of undesirable reduced elements [1].

Many metamorphic and sedimentary rocks can pollute groundwater. In natural waters, the pollution source may have four different origins [9, 10]: rocks that are essentially in carbonate form; accidental pollution; soil drainage; accumulation in the reducing zone of reservoir dams. The release of metals into groundwater does not pose a major risk to human health [11, 12], but they can pose problems in drinking water during its slow oxidation and its precipitation in the distribution network. [13, 14], summarized these problems as follows: they can give a metallic or bitter taste to the water; under certain conditions, deposits of iron oxide and manganese can occur causing certain inconveniences which are, among other things, stains on the linen, clogging of water softeners, deterioration of water quality due to bacterial development on the chemical medium of manganese oxide [15], etc. protection of bacteria against the biocidal effect of chlorine [16-18].

Senegal, as part of the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals in terms of access to water and sanitation, has installed many boreholes in rural areas since the 1970s [19]. Paradoxically, there are many problems relating to physical and chemical qualities, in particular: high levels of salt, fluorine, iron, manganese; the intrusion of undesirable elements from agricultural (pesticides, nitrates), mining (cyanide, arsenic and mercury) activities; risks of deterioration of the bacteriological quality of water due to lack of treatment, maintenance of hydraulic structures or appropriate sanitation systems, poor water transport and storage practices, unsanitary housing conditions [20, 21].

The general objective of this study is to make an inventory of the physical and chemical quality of groundwater in some areas of Senegal. Indeed, the specific objective related to this study is to see the representativeness of the physical and chemical parameters in terms of concentration in the groundwater of Senegal. To achieve this objective, we will apply the method of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and the Ascending Hierarchical Classification (HAC) of the statistical analysis tool *STATISTICA* for the statistical processing of the results of physical and chemical analyses.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Area

The samples were taken in the Dakar, Thiès, Louga, Matam, Kaolack, Tambacounda and Ziguinchor regions. To identify the samples, a number has been assigned to each bottle. The sampling equipment was given special attention. Thus, we used new polyethylene bottles. Before going to the field, the bottles are first washed with tap water, then with 10% nitric acid and finally rinsed thoroughly with distilled water. In the field before filling the bottles, as a safety measure, they are washed three (03) times with the water to be analyzed, then filled to the brim. The samples taken, carefully labeled and stored at 4 °C in coolers, are transported to the quality control analysis laboratory.

B. Methodologies and Equipment Used for the Assays

Two physical and chemical parameters (pH, electrical conductivity) were measured in-situ, immediately after sample collection. pH is measured in the field using a Radiometer Analytical pHM201 portable pH meter and in the laboratory using a Hanna pH209 laboratory pH meter. Conductivity is measured in the field using a Hanna brand portable conductivity meter. The turbidity is measured using a turbidimeter, turbidity meter WAg-WT 3020. Its unit is the NTU (Nephelometric Turbidity Unit). Sulfate and nitrate ions are determined by spectrophotometry or colorimetry using a Hach Lange DR 3800 spectrophotometer. Chloride ions are determined by the Mohr method. Calcium and magnesium ions are determined by complexometry using EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid). Iron and manganese were measured in the laboratory by colorimetry with a DR 2010/Hach type molecular absorption spectrophotometer.

C. Statistical Analysis

In this work we used the *STATISTICA* software as a data processing tool which could allow us in certain cases to better analyze the results and understand the basic sample matrix [22-24]. The technique of chemometrics makes it possible to correlate several variables in order to better understand the influence of several phenomena or constituents in diverse and varied samples in a space of reduced dimensions. There are several techniques used in chemometrics, including:

- **Principal Component Analysis (PCA)** which is a multidimensional descriptive method of a set of data. *PCA* is a statistical method that reduces a large initial number of more or less correlated variables to a small number of variables called factors or principal components, so that the observed variance is maximum [25-27]. These factors, not correlated with each other, are linear combinations of the initial variables.
- The principle of **Hierarchical Ascending Classification (HAC)** consists in creating a new partition of all the data by aggregating the two closest elements according to a distance chosen a priori [28, 29]. The hierarchical classifications determine a notion of paternity which results in a dendrogram indicating for each level, the grouping carried out.

The combined use of **Principal Component Analysis (PCA)** and **Ascending Hierarchical Classification (HAC)** is a powerful tool for analyzing physical and chemical parameters of mineral elements [30]. Data analysis focused on 10 parameters or variables: conductivity, pH, turbidity, Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , Mn^{2+} and total iron (Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+}). Indeed, the *PCA* is only valid when the studied factorial plans give more than 70% of information. The correlation between two elements is good, if it is close to 1. Correlation coefficients greater than 0.7 are thus considered significant, while those between 0.5 and 0.7 are considered less significant. In the case of the *CAH*, the euclidean distance was employed as a *similarity/dissimilarity* measure, while the Ward aggregation method was employed to link the bundles. A combination of euclidean distance as a measure of similarity and Ward's method as a method of aggregation has been observed as the best combination leading to optimal results in HAC [31, 32]. The mathematical basis of the method is based on the calculation of the Euclidean distance between individuals or observations in an n-dimensional space. First, the data must be normalized by calculating their means using the formula:

$$K_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij} - \bar{X}}{S_{iC}}$$

where K_{ij} is the normal value of X_{ij} for the i^{th} variable of the j^{th} individual, \bar{X} is the mean of the i^{th} variable and S_{iC} the standard deviation.

The procedure adopted gives equal weight to each variable. Thus, the similarity measure is simply the distance defined in a Euclidean space. The distance between two individuals (\mathbf{j} , \mathbf{k}) is given by the following relation:

$$d_{ij} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (K_{ik} - K_{jk}) \right]$$

Where K_{ik} represents the K^{th} variable measured on object \mathbf{i} , and K_{jk} the K^{th} variable measured on object \mathbf{j} . The result is given in the form of a vertical dendrogram which classifies the observations or variables by groups or sub-groups having the same weight or the same characteristics.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Physical and chemical characterization (**Table 1**) based on in situ measurements (pH, electrical conductivity, turbidity) and laboratory assay of major components and metallic trace elements (chloride Cl^- , sulphates SO_4^{2-} , nitrates NO_3^- , nitrites NO_2^- , calcium Ca^{2+} , magnesium Mg^{2+} , sodium Na^+ , total iron (Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+}), manganese Mg^{2+} , etc.) is made in seven (7) regions of Senegal.

Table 1: Characterization of borehole water in some areas of Senegal

Study area	Conductivity $\mu\text{S/cm}$	pH	Turbidity NTU	Cl ⁻ •F	SO ₄ ²⁻ mg/L	Ca ²⁺ •F	Mg ²⁺ •F	NO ₃ ⁻ mg/L	NO ₂ ⁻ mg/L	Total iron mg/L	Mn ²⁺ mg/L
Dakar	713,60 ^{a,b}	7,14 ^{b,c}	6,80 ^b	4,40 ^a	15,02 ^a	21,20 ^b	7,66 ^a	1,61 ^a	0,07 ^a	1,42 ^{b,c}	0,07 ^a
Thies	797,55 ^{a,b}	7,19 ^c	2,77 ^a	10,64 ^{a,b}	0,00 ^a	16,85 ^{a,b}	9,34 ^a	1,31 ^a	0,08 ^a	0,29 ^a	0,11 ^b
Louga	1122 ^{a,b}	7,66 ^d	7,02 ^{a,b}	3,00 ^{a,b}	280,00 ^c	13,60 ^{a,b}	8,40 ^a	0,80 ^{a,b}	0,13 ^a	0,47 ^{a,b}	0,132 ^a
Saint Louis	161,05 ^{a,c}	6,62 ^a	2,27 ^{a,b}	1,70 ^{a,b}	0,00 ^a	6,65 ^{a,b}	3,50 ^a	0,00 ^{a,b}	0,05 ^a	2,40 ^c	0,1 ^a
Kaolack	242 ^{a,c}	6,76 ^{a,b}	25,80 ^c	2,00 ^{a,b}	12,00 ^a	3,80 ^{a,b}	4,80 ^a	2,80 ^{a,b}	0,10 ^a	1,94 ^{b,c}	0,1 ^b
Tambacounda	211,50 ^{b,c}	7,16 ^{b,c}	1,45 ^{a,b}	2,50 ^{a,b}	2,50 ^a	5,15 ^a	4,15 ^a	1,40 ^{a,b}	0,09 ^a	0,11 ^a	0,08 ^a
Ziguinchor	1166,33 ^b	6,66 ^a	1,46 ^a	24,78 ^b	122,33 ^b	7,60 ^{a,b}	10,21 ^a	11,88 ^b	0,12 ^a	0,16 ^a	0,12 ^a

A. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) in groundwater

The results of the *PCA* were exploited by analysis of the correlation matrix and projection of different groundwaters in the factorial plan F₁-F₂.

B. Analysis of the correlation matrix

The analysis of the correlation matrix between parameters in groundwater is reported in *table 2*.

Table 2: Analysis of the correlation matrix between the physical and chemical analysis

	Cond	pH	Turb	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	NO ₃ ⁻	NO ₂ ⁻	Fe ²⁺	Mn ²⁺
Cond	1,00										
pH	0,41	1,00									
Turb	-0,22	0,02	1,00								
Cl ⁻	0,93	0,20	-0,20	1,00							
SO ₄ ²⁻	0,63	0,46	-0,15	0,44	1,00						
Ca ²⁺	0,29	0,40	0,009	0,14	-0,11	1,00					
Mg ²⁺	0,85	0,44	-0,09	0,78	0,49	0,21	1,00				
NO ₃ ⁻	0,03	-0,46	-0,09	0,05	-0,05	-0,21	-0,13	1,00			
NO ₂ ⁻	-0,03	-0,04	0,07	-0,05	-0,11	0,006	-0,09	0,21	1,00		
Fe ²⁺	-0,19	0,02	0,57	-0,16	-0,22	0,02	0,07	-0,15	-0,20	1,00	
Mn ²⁺	0,49	0,09	0,01	0,57	0,23	-0,11	0,31	0,32	-0,04	0,03	1,00

Examination of the correlation matrix clearly shows that pH and sulphate ions (SO₄²⁻) have negative correlations with nitrate ions (NO₃⁻) and total iron, respectively (-0.46) and (-0.22). This correlation shows an inversely proportional evolution of pH with SO₄²⁻ ions and indicates that groundwater samples have low levels of nitrate ions (NO₃⁻) and total iron. The matrix also reveals a good correlation (0.93) between the conductivity of the samples and the chloride ions (Cl⁻) which shows that the conductivity is mainly controlled by the Cl⁻ concentrations. Indeed, the measurement of the electrical conductivity makes it possible to evaluate quickly, but very approximately, the global mineralization of the water and to follow its evolution. The electrical conductivity values obtained vary between 161.5 and 1166.33 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ respectively

for the regions of Dakar, Thiès, Louga, Saint Louis, Kaolack, Tambacounda and the lower Casamance area (**Table 2**). The regions of Dakar, Thiès, Louga and lower Casamance have conductivity values higher than the *WHO* recommendation which is 300 $\mu\text{S/cm}$. We can say then, that these regions are highly mineralized. This mineralization could be explained by a surplus of the concentrations of certain metals in the water, because the more the concentration of the latter increases, the more the electrical conductivity increases [33-35].

C. Spatial groundwater analysis

The spatial analysis of the different groundwater samples and variables is presented in plan F₁-F₂ (**Figure 1 and 2**).

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